

TABLE 2

Compound	pH	C _H	Equivalent free H per mole of PMO ₁₂ O ₄₀	Equivalent of amine cation per mole of PMO ₁₂ O ₄₀	Apparent basicity of 12-Molybdo- phosphoric acid
1. Biguanidium 12-Molybdophosphate	2.23	0.005888	1.34	2.76	4.10
2. Guanylurea 12-Molybdophosphate	2.02	0.009550	1.27	2.79	4.06
3. Ethyl biguanidium 12-Molybdophosphate	2.13	0.007413	1.10	2.856	3.956
4. Phenylbiguanidium 12-Molybdophosphate	2.06	0.008710	1.127	3.116	4.243
5. Guanylurea-O-ethylether 12-Molybdophosphate	2.18	0.006607	1.37	2.664	4.034

Acknowledgement

The author thanks Mr. J. N. Roy, Head of the Department of Chemistry, Rammohan College, Calcutta for providing laboratory facilities and Dr. Santi Nandi of Jadavpur University for nitrogen estimation and thermal analysis.

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Proton-ligand Stability Constants of Substituted Ortho-Hydroxy Butyrophenones and their Oximes

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Manuscript received 17 June 1972; accepted 3 April 1973

THE knowledge of proton-ligand stability constants is a prerequisite for the calculation of metal-ligand stability constants. Again, these values are required to be determined accurately because the values of pL are dependent on them. The present work was undertaken because of our interest in exploring the equilibria which exist when metal ions interact with these ligands.

Experimental, Results and Discussion

The 3-methyl (3MeOHB), 4-methyl (4MeOHB) and 5-methyl (5MeOHB) derivatives of 2-hydroxy butyrophenone (OHB) and their oximes were prepared as described earlier^{1,2}.

An inert atmosphere was maintained by bubbling nitrogen gas through the solution. Potassium nitrate (B.D.H.) was used to keep the ionic strength constant. Standard carbonate-free sodium hydroxide (E. Merck) solution was prepared according to the method of Allen and Low³. Dioxane was purified by the method of Vogel⁴ and was freshly distilled before use. The pH measurements, the experimental technique and the methods of calculations of \bar{n}_H and 2K_H were the same as described earlier^{5,6}.

Although the oximes contain two dissociable protons, only one proton was observed to dissociate from any of the oximes. Thus all the oximes under study were considered as monobasic acids. The practical values of proton-ligand stability constants were calculated as described earlier⁵. The average values of practical constants obtained are summarized in Table 1. Verification of the results by duplicate experiments gave the log 2K_H values agreeing within ± 0.05 log unit.

The data in Table 1 show that introduction of a methyl group in any of the positions 3, 4 and 5 of the benzene nucleus results in weakening of the acid strength of OHB. This is consistent with electron releasing character of the methyl group.

The relative order of acid weakening effect obtained is 3Me \gg 4Me > 5Me. The relatively small difference in the pK values of 5MeOHB and 4MeOHB, which is almost within the estimated range of experimental error, raises some doubt as to the significance that could be attached to it. Nevertheless, the data do reflect the trend in the acid strength of these ketones.

3MeOHB is a considerably weaker acid than OHB. This may be attributed to the orthoposition of the methyl group in 3MeOHB. This will exert greater inductive effect on electron density at phenolic oxygen, force the -OH group to form hydrogen bond with keto group in all the molecules and increase hydrogen bond strength over that in OHB, and also decrease the stability of the anion of the acid due to the crowding by methyl group around the charge centre (O⁻) that would restrict the solvent molecules in their approach and interaction.

In 4MeOHB there is no forced orientation of -OH group which strengthens the hydrogen bond. However, inductive effect of the meta methyl group is expected to be smaller in view of enlarged distance

over which it has to operate. Also, $-O^-$ of the phenoxide ion is more roomier here than in 3MeOHB due to the distant position of the methyl group in 4MeOHB, so the stability of the phenoxide ion is relatively increased in 4MeOHB. Thus 4MeOHB is found to be stronger acid than 3MeOHB. What has been seen for 4MeOHB is also true for 5MeOHB. Therefore, 5MeOHB has an acid strength very close to that of 4MeOHB, or, it should be slightly stronger acid since the inductive effect would be expected to be even smaller. The data (Table 1) obtained support this prediction.

By substituting an oxime group for a keto oxygen and comparing their pK values (Tables 1), it was found that ketoximes are more acidic than the corresponding ketones. The substituting of a methyl group reduces the acidity of the parent ketoximes due to steric effect on the 'H-bond' between the phenolic 'OH' and 'N' of the oxime.

TABLE I. PROTON-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS:
MEDIUM: 75% DIOXANE—25% WATER (BY VOLUME)

Reagent	$\log PK^H$
2-OH-butyrophenone (OHB)	12.39
2-OH-3-CH ₃ -butyrophenone (3MeOHB)	13.24
2-OH-4-CH ₃ -butyrophenone (4MeOHB)	12.70
2-OH-5-CH ₃ -butyrophenone (5MeOHB)	12.67
2-OH-butyrophenoneoxime (OHBO)	11.81
2-OH-3-CH ₃ -butyrophenoneoxime (3MeOHBO)	12.16
2-OH-5-CH ₃ -butyrophenoneoxime (5MeOHBO)	11.90

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Further studies on Flemichapparin-A, a new chromenochalcone isolated from *Flemingia chappar**

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Manuscript received 2 August 1972; revised 19 January 1973;
accepted 7 April 1973

BASED on spectral evidence (UV, IR, NMR and Mass spectra), the structure of flemichapparin-A, a new chromenochalcone occurring in the whole plant of *Flemingia chappar* was first proposed as (I)¹.

* This work was presented at the 'Convention of Chemists' held at Allahabad University, Allahabad, October 8-12, 1972.

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At a later date, Merlini *et al* arrived at the same structure (I) for a new chromenochalcone², m.p. 191°-92°, isolated from the leaves or flowers of *F. chappar*². The properties of the latter agree with those of flemichapparin-A. We now furnish further independent chemical and spectral evidence in favour of the structure (I) for flemichapparin-A.

Catalytic hydrogenation of (I) with Adam's catalyst in alcohol furnished the corresponding tetrahydro-derivative, C₂₀H₂₂O₄ (M⁺ 326), m.p. 91°-92°, proving the presence of two easily reducible double bonds. The mass spectral data of the latter [m/e 326 (M⁺) 270, 221, 165 and 91] speak in favour of a chroman ring and two -OH groups in ring A. Thus, the chroman ring suffers the expected retro-Diels-Alder cleavage giving rise to a prominent peak at m/e 270 (M⁺-56; M⁺-CH₃C=CH₂). The occurrence

of the peaks at m/e 221 (M⁺-105; M⁺-C₆H₅CH₂CH₂), m/e 165 (m/e 270-C₆H₅CH₂CH₂) and m/e 91 (tropolium ion) proves that a dihydrocinnamoyl residue is present in tetrahydroflemichapparin-A. Ozonolysis of flemichapparin-A (I) furnished benzaldehyde as one of its reaction products thereby proving the unsubstituted nature of ring B.

The integrated 60 MHz NMR spectrum (Table 1) has also been found to be in excellent agreement with the structure (II) for tetrahydroflemichapparin-A. A sharp 1H-singlet at 7.11δ provides further evidence that it must be due to the C-6 proton as has been observed in the case of hexahydroflemingin-B (III)³ and hexahydroflemingin-C (IV)³ having similar 2,4,5-substitution pattern and identical attachment of the chroman ring. The UV spectrum [λ_{max}^{EtOH} 240 (log ε 3.66) 290 (log ε 4.17) and 350 nm (log ε 3.83)] of (II) also resembles that of hexahydroflemingin-B (III) and hexahydroflemingin-C (IV) thereby adding further corroborative evidence regarding the correctness of structure (II).

* Prof. Merlini (Milan) has agreed to retain the name flemichapparin-A first proposed by us (personal communication).